

***In vitro* hepatoprotective activity of *Cochlospermum religiosum* in BRL3A cell line**

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Abstract : Liver plays a major role in detoxification. Treatment of liver diseases is still a challenge to modern medicine. The allopathic medicine has been found to offer little in the alleviation of hepatic ailments whereas the most important representatives are of phytoconstituents. The *in vitro* hepatoprotective activity of various extracts of the plant *Cochlospermum religiosum* on the BRL3A (rat, liver cell line) cell line was carried out against paracetamol intoxication and the percentage viability of the cell line was determined. The cytotoxicity of *Cochlospermum religiosum* on rat liver cell was evaluated by the MTT assay [(3-(4,5-dimethylthiazole-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) assay]. Out of the various extracts evaluated, ethanolic extract of *Cochlospermum religiosum* gave promising results.

Keywords : Hepatoprotective, rat liver cell line, MTT, mitochondrial.

Introduction

Liver is one of the vital organs in human body which plays a major role in detoxification. So it has an important role in the maintenance, performance and in regulating homeostasis of the body¹. Management options for common liver diseases such as cirrhosis, fatty liver and chronic hepatitis are problematic. The conventional drugs used in the treatment of liver diseases viz. corticosteroids, antiviral and immunosuppressive agents are sometimes insufficient and may lead to serious adverse effects. It is there is a need to search alternative drugs for the treatment of liver disease to replace the currently used drugs of doubtful efficacy and safety².

In India, numerous medicinal plants are used for liver ailments in traditional systems of medicine. Some of these plants are evaluated for their hepatoprotective actions against hepatotoxins. However, the readily available hepatoprotective herbal drugs are not sufficiently effective in combating severe liver disorders. Therefore, there is a need to develop satisfactory hepatoprotective drugs.

Cochlospermum religiosum is a small deciduous tree belonging to the family Cochlospermaceae. The gum ob-

tained from this tree is known as katira. *Cochlospermum religiosum* (L). Traditionally it is used in treating cough, diarrhea, dysentery, pharyngitis, fistula, gonorrhoea, trachoma and syphilis. The dried leaf and flowers are used as stimulants, antipyretic, laxative and sedative³. In folk medicine this plant is found to be used as thermogenic, sedative and used in cough, diarrhea, dysentery, pharyngitis, gonorrhoea, syphilis and trachoma. It is used an ingredient in the Siddha Drug 'Kalnar Parpam' for its anti inflammatory property⁴. Its leaves are traditionally used to treat jaundice and liver diseases⁵. *Cochlospermum religiosum* root is found to be hepatoprotective⁶. Traditionally the bark is used for treating jaundice⁷. It has also shown broad spectrum activity and therefore used to treat microbial infections⁸.

After review of published literature showing its medicinal importance, the present protocol has outlined regarding the *in vitro* hepatoprotective activity on this selected plant using different extracts. In the present study, we selected the plant *Cochlospermum religiosum* and investigated the hepatoprotective effect of the plant extracts against paracetamol induced liver injury *in vitro* using

different extracts (petroleum ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate, ethyl alcohol, distilled water) against paracetamol induced toxicity.

Experimental

Plant source :

The stem bark of *Cochlospermum religiosum* is obtained from the local market, Tirunelveli, and identified by Professor V. Chelladurai, Botanist, Tirunelveli, Tamilnadu.

Extraction :

200 g of powdered material of *Cochlospermum religiosum* was taken in Soxhlet and extracted with various solvent. Later the dry extract was obtained by evaporating extracted solvent under reduced pressure. The yield of the extraction was obtained.

Cell lines and culture medium⁹ :

BRL3A (rat, liver cell line) cell lines were obtained from National Centre for Cell Sciences (NCCS), Pune, India. Stock cells of BRL3A were maintained and cultured in Dulbecco's modified eagles medium supplemented with 10% inactivated Foetal Bovine Serum (FBS), penicillin (100 IU/ml), streptomycin (100 µg/ml) and amphotericin B (5 µg/ml) in an humidified atmosphere of 5% CO₂ at 37 °C until the cell reaches confluence. The cells were dissociated with trypsin-phosphate-versene-glucose solution (0.2% trypsin, 0.02% EDTA, 0.05% glucose in PBS). The stock cultures were cultured in 25 cm² culture flasks and 96 microtitre plates (Tarsons India Pvt. Ltd., Kolkata, India) were used to carry out all experiments.

Preparation of test solutions :

For cytotoxicity studies, a stock solution of 1 mg/ml concentration was prepared by separately dissolving each weighed test drugs in distilled DMSO and volume was made up with DMEM supplemented with 2% inactivated FBS. The stock solution was sterilized by filtration. Serial two fold dilutions were prepared from the above stock solution for carrying out cytotoxic studies.

Determination of cell viability by MTT assay¹⁰ :

The monolayer cell culture was trypsinized and using DMEM medium containing 10% FBS, the cell count was adjusted to 1.0 × 10⁵ cells/ml. The diluted cell suspen-

sion (approximately 10,000 cells) of 0.1 ml was added to each well of the 96 well microtitre plate. When a partial monolayer was formed after 24 h, the supernatant was flicked off, the monolayer was once washed with medium. The plates were then incubated at 37 °C for 3 days in 5% CO₂ atmosphere in the presence of 100 µL of different concentrations of test drugs. The microscopic examination was carried out and observations were noted every 24 h interval. After 48 h, the test solutions in the wells were removed and 50 µL of 3-(4,5-dimethyl-2-thiazolyl)-2,5-diphenyl-tetrazolium bromide (MTT) in phosphate-buffered saline solution was added to each well. The plates were gently shaken and incubated at 37 °C in 5% CO₂ atmosphere. After 3 h incubation the supernatant was removed and 100 µL of propanol was added to the plates with gentle shaking to solubilize the formed formazan. A microplate reader was used to measure the absorbance at a wavelength of 540 nm. The percentage growth inhibition was calculated using the following formula and concentration of test drug needed to inhibit cell growth by 50% (CTC₅₀) values is generated from the dose-response curves for each cell line.

Determination of hepatoprotective activity¹² :

The same above experimental procedure was followed. The percentage cell viability was determined, based on which the percentage protection offered by test and standard drugs was calculated over the ethanol control.

Statistical analysis :

Data are expressed as means ± SEM. Mean difference between groups were analysed by Student 't' test. *p* value < 0.001 was considered to be statistically significant.

Results and discussion

Table 1. Percentage of yield of *Cochlospermum religiosum* with given solvents

Sl. no.	Solvent	Appearance	% of yield
1.	Petroleum ether	Green	1.4
2.	Chloroform	Green	0.8
3.	Ethyl acetate	Green	1.4
4.	Ethyl alcohol	Green	12.4
5.	Distilled water	Green	19.22

Table 2. Cytotoxic property of test drug *Cochlospermum religiosum* in BRL3A cell line by MTT assay

Sl. no.	Test drug	CTC ₅₀ in µg/ml
1.	Pet ether	> 1000
2.	Ethyl acetate	333.33 ± 1.3
3.	Chloroform	383.33 ± 2.0
4.	Alcohol	293.33 ± 0.7
5.	Aqueous	310.00 ± 0.6

Table 3. Hepatoprotective study of *Cochlospermum religiosum* in BRL3A cell line

Sl. no.	Test drug	Test concn. in µg/ml	% Protection offered over toxicant control
1.	Control (Untreated cells)		100 ± 0
2.	Paracetamol	4000	0 ± 0 ^a
3.	Pet ether	400	0 ± 0 ^a
4.	Chloroform	200	4.64 ± 1.06 ^a
5.	Ethyl acetate	200	16.74 ± 0.24 ^{a,b}
6.	Alcohol	100	15.72 ± 4.02 ^{a,b}
7.	Aqueous	150	0.00 ± 0.00 ^{a,b}
8.	Silymarin	200	41.35 ± 0.36 ^{a,b}

*All values are mean ± S.E.M. $n = 6$, ^a $p < 0.001$ when compared to untreated cells. ^b $p < 0.001$ when compared to paracetamol intoxicated cells.

The individual parts of an organism and their effective organization will clearly determine their longevity. The evaluation for hepatoprotective activity was carried out on various solvent extracts of *Cochlospermum religiosum* plant and shows a fairly good prospective use of it for the same in future. The cell take up tetrazolium salt (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazole-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl-tetrazolium bromide) and it is reduced in a mitochondrial dependent reaction to yield a blue coloured product called as formazan. The capability of cells to produce formazan by reducing MTT provides a proof for mitochondrial integrity and activity which in turn may be used as a measure of viability and/or cell number. From the above results it is observed that cells which are exposed only with toxicant paracetamol showed a percentage viability of 0% while cells which are pretreated with test drugs showed an increase in percentage viability and the results were highly significant ($p < 0.001$, when compared to paracetamol intoxicated cells). The percentage viability

ranged from 4 to 16% cell viability, when compared to standard drug silymarin which showed 41% viability.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the present observations provide preliminary data exposing the various solvent extracts of *Cochlospermum religiosum* exhibiting moderate toxicity against BRL3A cell line and CTC₅₀ value for these drugs was found to be in range of 250 to 400 µg/ml.

Among the various solvent extracts of *Cochlospermum religiosum* alcoholic extract showed better protection when compared with other solvent extracts. Standard drug, silymarin showed significant activity with 41.35 ± 0.36 percent cell protection.

This calls for further studies on the active components for proper assessment of their therapeutic properties as well as their possible development as promising anti-hepatotoxic drug.

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